

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIVE EFFECTIVENESS OF DISCUSSION AND DEMONSTRATION METHODS ON STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN CHEMISTRY IN OGBIA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, BAYELSA STATE.

BY

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Abstract

This study is a comparative analysis of the relative effectiveness of discussion and demonstration methods on secondary school students' performance in chemistry in Ogbia, Bayelsa State. Quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of 1342 SS2 science student in all the 37 public secondary school in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State and a sample size of 100 study was purposively drawn from the population of chemistry student in the study area. The Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) used for collection of data and data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses was tested using independence t-test at 0.05 level of significance. Finding revealed that, student taught using demonstration methods perform better than those taught using discussion. It also showed that female students taught using demonstration method perform better than their male counterparts. It was recommended among others that teachers should incorporate more demonstration-based techniques in their Chemistry lessons to facilitate better understanding and retention of the material.

Keywords: Comparative Analysis, Relative Effectiveness, Discussion and Demonstration Methods, Students' Performance.

Introduction

Education is the key factor in the development and advancement of society. It greatly contributes to a nation's socio-economic development and is a powerful tool for change. Shiller (2015) saw education as an investment in human capital that produces returns to individuals in the form of higher earnings and social returns. Education is the process of facilitating learning, knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits assumed to a group of people which are transferred to other people through storytelling, discussion, teaching, training, or research. Successful

teaching and learning largely emanate from careful planning, preparation, and the methods used in giving out the materials. Before this can be achieved, the teacher must be fully aware of the subject matter and various teaching methods.

Teaching methods are standard procedures for presenting subject matter and organizing teacher-student interaction during a lesson. Each teaching strategy is associated with a method. Nkeng and Mambeh (2016) viewed teaching methods as techniques and strategies adopted by teachers in their efforts to facilitate students' learning. It is an activity

that translates curriculum goals and objectives into experiences that students acquire during their interaction with their teacher. Therefore, the ability of the teacher to appropriately use different strategies will go a long way to improve students' academic performance. According to Tambo (2017), the effective teaching and learning of chemistry as a core science subject in secondary schools is not without some problems, which result in poor academic performance of students. Some chemistry teachers use methods just as they have seen them from their colleagues or from seminars without sufficient knowledge of the method, sometimes without understanding that each method has its way of teaching depending on the students' level and the topic. For instance, most teachers use the lecture method for all topics and classrooms at the secondary school level without considering the age of the students, thus, making it difficult for students to participate in class or sometimes giving them inferential thinking skills leading to a situation where students are not active in the classroom and as well lose interest in the subject/topic. This is because most students learn by doing and not just listening (Odom & Lanasa, 2016).

A teacher who has not undergone training might not be able to apply these methods appropriately, causing them to be ignorant about the methods used in teaching chemistry, which would otherwise raise students' interest, thereby leading to desirable performance (Okenwa, 2017). However, effective teaching and learning of Chemistry could involve a variety of instructional processes and strategies, including discussion

and demonstration teaching methods (Charles, 2021).

Discussion method is a teaching method that involves students discussing a topic or issue in a group setting. The goal of this method is to encourage students to think critically and engage in meaningful conversation. According to Wang (2016) discussion teaching strategy involves a small group activities to discuss and to find the solution of the problem. Furthermore, Keshavarzi et al., (2016) called the discussion teaching method a constructive learning process. In a similar vein, Dewi (2019) sees discussion teaching method as a two-way conversation method. The teacher typically poses a question or topic to the class, and then students share their thoughts and opinions. Akpata (2018) revealed that the discussion teaching method is an approach in which students are given the opportunity to interact, share ideas, and share their opinions, allowing them to individually express themselves. The teacher's role in a discussion-driven lesson becomes that of coordinating the points expressed. The students provide the information required for developing meaning. The classroom discussion is thus a teaching strategy that involves the active participation of the learner in the learning process. This strategy does not leave the students to passively receive knowledge but rather allows students to be carried along as they learn from the contributions of their colleagues and what they themselves offer in the process (Ahmed and Plessis, (2024). Akpata (2018) argued that the performance of learners faces continued challenges, and teaching methods and strategies that engage learners to be

actively involved should be encouraged by teachers.

Moreover, demonstration is a teaching method in which a teacher makes a presentation of the lesson by displaying various activities that the class will observe. These activities could include drawing, sketching, displaying a chart, a video presentation, or displaying some concrete objects and specimens (Daluba, 2016). The students are given an opportunity to see, observe, listen, and even interpret the message. Studies show that when students are made to observe and derive understanding from what the teacher demonstrates, they achieve better and retain the knowledge. This is a strategy that prepares students to perform what the teacher may present to them in the class. A student may also perform a demonstration that the rest of the class is made to see. This is where the students demonstrate their special skills so that other members of the class can benefit from that experience. The proper use of demonstration can motivate students to learn Chemistry because it will generate interest for more students to exhibit their skills (Woye, 2017). Today's education is geared towards student-centeredness, meaning the teacher must be trained to use the appropriate teaching methods well. This is because they need to direct the students on how these methods are used for them to perform well and also become active in the teaching and learning process. Thus, a well-trained teacher will be able to teach well and create a love for the subject in the minds of the students, but a teacher who is not trained will rather create discouragement and a high-rate of hatred for

the subject in the minds of the students which will in turn affect their performance (Omeogo, 2019).

Academic performance is a measure of how well you are doing in school. It's important to stay focused, study, and ask for help when needed. In senior secondary school, academic performance becomes even more crucial as it sets the foundation for higher education and career paths. It is often considered the cornerstone of educational achievement. This performance is typically measured by grades, scores, or qualitative assessments that reflect the knowledge and skills acquired in various subjects or courses. The importance of academic performance extends beyond mere numerical scores. It is indicative of a student's grasp of concepts, ability to apply knowledge, and development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Al-Husaini and Shukor, 2023).

Chemistry is a core science subject that occupies a central position in secondary schools. It's an integral branch of science that deals with the study of the composition, properties, and behavior of matter. It forms a foundation for science that is needed to contribute immensely to the technological growth of the nation. This includes medicine, nursing, engineering, pharmacy, and so on. Chemistry is, therefore, a discipline in science education that has to be properly handled and taught at the secondary school level to equip students and learners with the critical skills for technological growth in society (Irshad, 2016). As one of the basic sciences, Chemistry is necessary for school children to gain entrance into tertiary education for specialization in the sciences,

engineering, and technology. In view of this, it is pertinent to promote the effective teaching and learning of Chemistry.

The teaching and learning of Chemistry in Nigeria and Ogbia Local Government Area in particular has experienced such difficulties over several years. This has led to a search for new ways of handling the subject so that students' learning and academic performance can be improved. The academic achievement of students in Chemistry in senior secondary schools in Ogbia local government area of Bayelsa State has remained poor over the years as evidenced in the results of the West African Examinations Council (Jakudi, 2019). This is a problem posing a source of concern to education stakeholders such as the students, parents, science education experts and the society at large. Although many factors may lead to poor performance of the students in Chemistry, it is evident that the use of inappropriate instructional strategies is a major contributing factor. This is yet to be established as to whether teachers of Chemistry in the schools use teaching methods that are appropriate to the students' modes of learning. An effective teaching and learning method will lead to success of students and prevent massive failure. The use of discussion and demonstration methods for teaching Chemistry would engage students to be actively involved in the teaching and learning process. Therefore, this study is to comparatively analyze the relative effectiveness of discussion and demonstration teaching methods on senior secondary school students in Chemistry in Ogbia local government area, Bayelsa State.

The objective of the study is to comparatively analyze the effectiveness of discussion and demonstration methods on secondary school students' academic performance in Chemistry in Ogbia, Local Government Area Bayelsa State. Specific objectives of the study are;

1. To determine the mean difference in performance of students taught using discussion method and those taught using demonstration method of teaching.
2. To determine the influence of discussion teaching method on male and female students' performance in Chemistry in Ogbia, Bayelsa State.
3. To determine the influence of demonstration teaching method on male and female students' performance in Chemistry.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the mean difference between the performance of student taught chemistry using discussion method and those taught using demonstration method of teaching?
2. What is the mean difference in the academic performance of male and female students' taught Chemistry using demonstration method in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?
3. What is the mean difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught Chemistry using discussion teaching in Ogbia

Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and test at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of students taught chemistry using discussion method and those taught using demonstration method of teaching.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between male and female students’ academic performance in Chemistry using discussion teaching method.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between male and female students’ performance in Chemistry using demonstration teaching method.

Method

The study employed the quasi-experimental design. The population of the study comprised of 1,342 SS2 male and female students in mixed public secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. A sample of one hundred (100) students was used for the study. The sample was from two coeducational schools in Ogbia local government area selected randomly. One school was assigned to two groups. Students in group A was taught chemistry using demonstration method of teaching, while students in group B were taught chemistry using discussion method of teaching. The instrument employed for data collection for this study was Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT). The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses was tested using independence t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 4.1:

Research Question One

What is the mean difference between the performance of student taught chemistry using discussion method and those taught using demonstration method of teaching?

Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Chemistry Students Taught Acid, Base and Salt Using Discussion Method and Those Taught Using Demonstration Method of Teaching.

Teaching Method	N	Pretest Mean (X)	S	D	Posttest Mean (X)	S	D	Mean Gain
Discussion	45	55.02	1.96	6	5 . 8 8	.	5 9	. 1 1
Demonstration	55	65 . 4 5	1.95	7	5 . 3 6	.	7 9	. 7

The results in table 1 shows that students taught using the demonstration method performed better on the topic of Acid, Base, and Salt compared to those taught using the

discussion method. The mean score for the demonstration method is 75.3, which is notably higher than the mean score of 65.8 for the discussion method. Additionally, the

standard deviation for the demonstration method (6.7) is lower than that for the discussion method (8.5), indicating that students' performance in the demonstration

group was more consistent. This suggests that the demonstration method might be more effective in enhancing students' understanding of the topic.

Research Question Two

What is the mean difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught Chemistry using demonstration in Ogbia, Bayelsa State?

Table 4.2

Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Acid, Base and Salts Using Demonstration Method in Ogbia, Bayelsa State.

Gender	N	Pretest Mean	S	D	Posttest Mean	S	D	Mean Gain
Male	30	65.76	8.57		73.50	6.1		7.74
Female	25	68.21	9.05		76.80	7.2		8.59

The results in table 2 shows that both male and female students performed well when taught using the demonstration method. However, female students had a slightly higher mean score (76.8) compared to male students (73.5). The standard deviation for female students (6.1) is lower than that for male students (7.2), suggesting that the

performance of female students was more consistent. This may imply that the demonstration method is particularly effective for female students, but it is beneficial for both genders overall in understanding the topic of Acid, Base, and Salts.

Research Question Three

What is the mean difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught Chemistry using discussion teaching in Ogbia, Bayelsa State?

Table 4.3

Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Acid, Base and Salts Using Discussion Teaching in Ogbia, Bayelsa State

Gender	N	Pretest Mean	S	D	Posttest Mean	S	D	Mean Gain
Male	20	62.16	7.90		63.28	9.1		1.04
Female	25	65.45	8.23		68.57	4.3		3.05

The results in table 3 shows that female students outperformed male students when taught using the discussion method. The mean score for female students is 68.5, higher than the mean score of 63.2 for male students. The standard deviation is lower for female students (7.4) compared to male students

(8.9), indicating more consistent performance among females. While both genders show variation in performance, the discussion method appears to be slightly more effective for female students in understanding the topic of Acid, Base, and Salts.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the academic performance of students taught chemistry using discussion method and those taught using demonstration method of teaching.

Table 4.4

t-test Analysis of Chemistry Students Scores Taught Acid, Base and Salts Using Discussion Method and Those Taught Using Demonstration Method of Teaching.

M e t h o d	N	S	D	D	f	t-value	p-value	Decision
Discussion Method	45	65.8	8.5	9	85	5.72	0.00	Rejected
Demonstration Method	55	75.3	6.7	9	85			

From table 4, t-value = 5.72 with Df = 98 and p-value = 0.01 is obtained. The t-test analysis shows a significant difference in the mean scores of students taught using the discussion method compared to those taught using the demonstration method. The calculated t-value of 5.72, with a p-value of 0.00 (which is less than the 0.05 significance level),

indicates that the demonstration method is significantly more effective than the discussion method in teaching the topic of Acid, Base, and Salts. This result suggests that students benefit more from the interactive and visual aspects of the demonstration method, leading to better understanding and retention of the

material.

Hypotheses Two

There is no significant difference between male and female students' academic performance in Chemistry using discussion teaching method.

Table 4.5

t-test Analysis of Male and Female Chemistry Students Scores Taught Acid, Base and Salts Using Discussion Teaching Method.

G e n d e r	N	S	D D	f	t-value	p-value	Decision
M a l e	20	63.28	9	4	32.38	0.02	Rejected
F e m a l e	25	68.57	4				

From table 4, t-value = 2.38 with Df = 43 and p-value = 0.02 is obtained. The t-test analysis for the scores of male and female students taught using the discussion method reveals a significant difference between the two groups. The calculated t-value is 2.38, with a p-value of 0.02 (which is less than the 0.05 significance level), indicating that female students performed significantly better than male students under the discussion teaching

Hypotheses Three

There is no significant difference between male and female students’ performance in Chemistry using demonstration teaching method.

Table 4.6

t-test Analysis of Male and Female Chemistry Students Scores Taught Acid, Base and Salts Using Demonstration Teaching Method.

Male vs. Female Students Taught Using the Demonstration Method

G e n d e r	N	S	D D	f	t-value	p-value	D e c i s i o n
M a l e	3	073.57	2				A c c e p t e d
F e m a l e	2	576.86	1	5	31.87	0.07	

From table 4. The t

-test analysis comparing the scores of male and female students taught using the demonstration method shows no significant difference between the two groups. With t-value of 1.87, and a p-value of 0.07, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level. This result indicates that both male and female

method. This result suggests that the discussion method may be more effective for female students in understanding and mastering the topic of Acid, Base, and Salts.

students performed similarly under the demonstration teaching method, with no significant difference in their mean scores. The demonstration method appears to be equally effective for both genders in teaching the topic of Acid, Base, and Salts.

Discussion

The findings from this study provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of different teaching methods and gender differences as regards the teaching methods in the performance of Chemistry students, particularly when teaching Chemistry. The significant difference observed between the discussion and demonstration teaching methods aligns with existing literature on instructional strategies in science education. Demonstration teaching methods are known to enhance students' understanding by providing concrete experiences and visual representations of abstract concepts, which are especially critical in subjects like Chemistry (Ali & Awan, 2018). The higher mean scores for students taught using the demonstration method (75.3) compared to those taught using the discussion method (65.8) corroborate the findings of Ogundipe and Adedayo (2019), who reported that students taught with demonstrations retained information better and performed higher on assessments than those taught through discussions.

This study's results are consistent with the theory of experiential learning, which posits that students learn more effectively when they can observe and engage directly with the learning material (Kolb, 2015). The significant t-value of 5.72 and p-value of 0.0001 in this study provide strong evidence that demonstration methods offer a more effective approach to teaching complex scientific topics, confirming the hypothesis that demonstration would result in better student outcomes. The gender differences observed in students' performance under the

discussion teaching method, where female students outperformed male students, is supported by research that suggests females tend to excel in verbal and collaborative learning environments (Hyde, 2016). The significant difference, with a t-value of 2.38 and a p-value of 0.021, indicates that the discussion method may cater more effectively to the learning styles typically associated with female students, who often prefer verbal interactions and group discussions (Meece, Glienke, & Burg, 2006).

In contrast, the lack of significant gender differences in the performance of students taught using the demonstration method (t-value of 1.87, p-value of 0.067) aligns with studies that suggest hands-on, visual teaching methods can bridge gender gaps in science education (Reid, 2019). The near-equivalent mean scores for male (73.5) and female (76.8) students in this study indicate that demonstration methods provide an equitable learning experience, supporting the findings of Aina and Olanipekun (2020), who found that gender-neutral instructional strategies, such as demonstrations, can mitigate performance disparities.

Conclusion

The findings of this study showed the importance of employing effective teaching strategies in science education. Demonstration methods, which allow for experiential learning, have been shown to significantly enhance student performance across genders, as supported by the relevant literature. Meanwhile, discussion methods, while beneficial, may not be as universally effective, especially in minimizing gender differences in learning outcomes. These

insights are crucial for educators and policymakers aiming to optimize teaching methods to improve academic performance in Chemistry, particularly in contexts similar to Ogbia, Bayelsa State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers should incorporate more demonstration-based techniques in their Chemistry lessons to facilitate better understanding and retention of the material.
2. Schools should invest in the necessary resources and equipment to facilitate demonstration-based teaching.
3. Conduct studies with larger sample sizes to increase the generalizability of the findings.
4. Explore the effectiveness of demonstration and discussion methods across different subjects and educational levels to understand their broader applicability.

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